

Investigation Of The Critical and Creative Thinking Levels Of Students In Combined Classes¹

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Abstract

This study aims to determine whether the critical and creative thinking skills of students studying in combined classes differ in terms of various variables. In this context, a mixed method was used in the study. The study group consists of 21 students studying in combined 3rd and 4th grades. Three data collection tools were used as data collection tools: “Semi-Structured Interview Form Including Creativity and Renewal Questions” prepared by the researcher, “21st Century Learning and Renewal Skills Scale” and “Critical Thinking Dispositions Scale Turkish Version” prepared by Uluçınar and Akar. Some steps were taken to increase the validity and reliability of the research and the data were examined through descriptive analysis. When the research results were examined, a moderate relationship was found between teachers' creative thinking dispositions and their creativity encouraging behaviors. This result indicates that as teachers' creative thinking dispositions increase, they show creativity encouraging behavior more frequently. The observation results of the students' sub-skills of both scales; According to the grade level variable, a significant difference was found for the 3rd graders in the sub-dimensions of Curiosity and Questioning and Attention and Skepticism; while a significant difference was found in favor of the 4th graders in the sub-dimensions of Maturity and Open-Mindedness, Bias/Objectivity, Creativity and Renewal, Critical Thinking and Problem Solving and Communication and Collaboration.

Keywords: Combined classes, Critical thinking skills, Creative thinking skills, Classroom education

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1. Introduction

Combined classes are a practice that has been used not only in our time but also in previous periods. It is an undeniable fact that various factors influenced the decision to resort to this practice. Unfortunately, such practices continue to be a festering wound in our country's primary education system. It can be easily seen that constructive solutions are being developed for the implementation of combined classes in our country and other regions. As with all activities related to education, schools take the lead in these activities as well. Schools are important because they provide environments where students can acquire knowledge, access information, and express themselves freely. Although the reasons for implementing combined-class schools vary worldwide, in Türkiye they have become an integral part of our education system, having been in practice since the early years of the Republic (Sadık et al., 2022). According to the 2022-2023 academic year statistics in Türkiye: the number of schools with combined classes was 6.326, the number of teachers working in combined classes was 6.603, and the number of students studying in combined classes was 135.924 (Koda, 2023).

Students in combined classes need to acquire critical and creative thinking skills in order to keep pace with the demands of this century. Critical thinking, as one of the modes of thinking, is considered to be the process of analyzing events and phenomena, interpreting and evaluating the root cause of a problem based on scientific process steps, before deciding on a solution (Kaya, 1998). In this context, it has been shown that the key to a developed society lies in raising individuals who can ask questions, solve problems, and produce critical and creative ideas in the face of challenges, which are considered indicators of a developed society (Şen, 2009). In other words, it has become essential to cultivate individuals who, through their education, learn effective learning, can solve problems using unconventional methods, can utilize critical and creative thinking skills, and are open to continuous development (Ay, 2005).

Critical and creative thinking skills are among the philosophical thinking skills. These thinking skills influence each other and develop together (Akkocaoğlu Çayır, 2021). Considered a prerequisite for creative thinking, critical thinking guides thought according to its established criteria and aims to arrive at a logical judgment. Research has shown that these skills can be acquired and developed from an early age. Children can acquire skills within the social groups they are a part of from a young age. It has been suggested that philosophy education would be beneficial for children, especially those in primary school, in developing their critical and creative thinking skills. These philosophical educations also have different approaches. Some of these methods and programs include Matthew Lipman's P4C Programs, Nelson's Socratic Method, Thomas E. Jackson Method, Gareth Mathews Method, PIS (Philosophical Inquiry Society) Method, Guided Socratic Discussion Programs, Oscar Brenifier's Socratic Method, Jacques Levine Method, and SAPERE (Society for Advancing Philosophical Enquiry and Reflection in Education) (Daşdelen, 2021; Erdoğan, 2018). Philosophy can be used as a tool to develop critical and creative thinking skills in elementary school children. In other words, the child does not need to be taught philosophical disciplines or learn a subject (Lipman, 2011).

The aim of this study is to determine whether the critical and creative thinking skills of students studying in combined classes differ according to various variables. In this context, answers have been sought to some sub-problems;

1. To what extent have the observations of teachers working in combined classes contributed to the development of critical and creative thinking skills?

2. To what extent does gender affect the critical and creative thinking of students studying in combined classes?
3. To what level do students in combined classes possess critical and creative thinking sub-skills, according to their grade level?
4. According to observation results, to what extent is critical and creative thinking related to the sub-skills of students studying in combined classes?

2. Methodology

This study, which examined the critical and creative thinking levels of students in combined classes, employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative research methods for data collection and analysis. The main purpose of using a mixed methods approach is to broaden and explain the research question, and to use both qualitative and quantitative methods together in this explanation (Karasar, 2019).

2.1. Population and Sample

The sample for this study consists of 21 students who were enrolled in combined classes in two schools in the Eğil and Bağlar districts of Diyarbakır province during the 2023-2024 academic year.

2.2. Data Collection Tools

Data for the research was collected using a semi-structured interview form that included scales on Critical Thinking Tendencies and 21st Century Learning and Innovation Skills, as well as questions on Creativity and Innovation.

2.3. Data Collection Process

The necessary permissions were obtained for the use of the scales and observation form, and the study was conducted on a voluntary basis. Observation was conducted in three phases: pre-process, during the process, and post-process. The application of the scales and the observation process took approximately one month.

2.4. Data Analysis

The quantitative data obtained within the scope of the research were analyzed in line with the objectives of the research. Statistical analyses were performed using the SPSS software package. Descriptive analysis method was used in the analysis of qualitative data. In descriptive analysis, the data described in this type of research are interpreted by the researcher. This interpretation is not done in depth or comprehensively. The researcher interprets and presents the lengthy conversations, descriptions, behaviors, rumors, and interview notes. It does not present all the data obtained. Instead, it selects the data it has chosen, or reduced, and writes them down in a specific order. Then the comments. The researcher's primary task here is to show what reality looks like and to add conceptual frameworks to it (Sönmez & Alacapınar, 2013).

3. Findings

This section presents the research findings and information regarding the sub-problems.

3.1. Findings Regarding the First Sub-Problem

The findings for the first sub-problem are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Independent Samples T-Test Results Regarding the Contributions of Creative Thinking and Critical Thinking Skills Based on Observations

Variables	N	X	SS	t	SD	p	ES
Observation Critical Thinking	21 21	31,71	6,55	22,15	1,43	0,000	7,33
Observation Creative Thinking	21 21	21,23	6,43	15,12	1,40	0,000	4,64

The mean score they received from the observational assessment on the critical thinking tendencies scale was 31.71 with a standard deviation of 6.55, while the mean score they received from the observational assessment on the 21st-century learning and innovation skills scale was 21.23 with a standard deviation of 6.43. A p-value of 0.05 or less indicates a significant difference between related groups. In this context, it was observed that the p-values ($0.00 < 0.05$) were small between the mean scores obtained from the 21st century learning and renewal skills scale ($t(1,40) = 15.12$, $p < 0.05$) and the critical thinking tendencies scale ($t(1,43) = 22.15$, $p < 0.05$) and that there was a statistically significant difference.

3.2. Findings Regarding the Second Sub-Problem

The findings for the second sub-problem are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Independent Samples T-Test Results Regarding Creative Thinking and Critical Thinking Skills by Gender

Variables	Gender	N	X	SD	t	p	ES
Creative Thinking	Female	12	38,1	1,52	,497	,625	5,43
	Male	9	37,88	,781			
Critical Thinking	Female	12	48,9	2,23	,829	,420	1,29
	Male	9	48,0	2,69			

It was found that the average scores of female students were higher than the average scores of male students. A t-test was applied to the mean scores of the groups to determine whether this difference was significant. According to the results of the independent samples t-test: no statistically significant difference was found between the mean scores of genders on the 21st century learning and renewal skills scale ($t(19) = ,497$, $p < 0,01$). The mean score for girls on the critical thinking tendencies scale was 48.9 with a standard deviation of 2.23, while the mean score for boys was 48.0 with a standard deviation of 2.69. According to the results of the independent samples t-test, there was a significant difference in the mean scores of the critical thinking tendencies scale between genders ($t(15,4) = ,829$, $p < 0.01$).

3.3. Findings Regarding the Third Sub-Problem

The findings for the third sub-problem are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Statistical Results Regarding Critical and Creative Thinking Sub-Skills by Grade Level

Group Statistics						
Variables	Grade	N	X	SD	t	p
Critical Thinking	3rd	15	48,53	2,61	,030	,977
	4rd	6	48,5	2,07		
Maturity and Open-mindedness	3rd	15	11,53	1,84	-1,39	,219
	4rd	6	12,5	1,22		
Caution and Skepticism	3rd	15	15,13	1,24	,583	,588
	4rd	6	14,83	,983		
Curiosity and Inquiry	3rd	15	15,46	1,35	2,17	,485
	4rd	6	14,0	1,41		
Bias and Objectivity	3rd	15	6,40	,736	,3,03	,018
	4rd	6	7,16	,408		
Creativity and Innovation	3rd	15	27,46	2,66	-2,27	0,039
	4rd	6	30,66	3,01		
Critical Thinking and Problem Solving	3rd	15	27,26	3,08	-1,39	,449
	4rd	6	28,83	1,94		
Communication and Cooperation	3rd	15	12,93	2,31	-2,25	0,048
	4rd	6	15,16	1,94		

It was found that the average scores of 3rd-grade students on the critical thinking sub-skill were higher than the average scores of 4th-grade students. In this case, a statistically significant difference was determined between the average scores they received ($t(,754) = ,030, p < 0,01$).

It was determined that the average scores of 3rd-year students on the maturity and open-mindedness sub-skill were higher than the average scores of 4th-year students. In this case, a statistically significant difference was found between the average scores they received ($t(,494) = ,0219, p < 0,01$).

It was found that the average scores of 3rd-grade students on the sub-skills of attentiveness and skepticism differed by 1.46 points in favor of 3rd-grade students compared to 4th-grade students. In this case, a statistically significant difference was found between the average scores they received ($t(,361) = ,588, p < 0,01$).

It was observed that the average scores of 3rd-grade students on the curiosity and inquiry sub-skill differed by 1.46 points from the average scores of 4th-grade students, favoring the 3rd-grade students. In this case, a statistically significant difference was determined between the average scores they received ($t(,493) = ,0485, p < 0,01$).

A difference of 0.76 points was found between the average scores obtained by 3rd-year students and 4th-year students on the sub-skill of Bias and Objectivity, to the disadvantage of the 3rd-year students. In this case, a statistically significant difference was found between the average scores they received ($t(,954) = ,039, p < 0,01$).

A difference of 3.20 points was found between the average scores obtained by 3rd-year students and 4th-year students in the creativity and innovation sub-skill, with the 3rd-year students scoring less than the 4th-year students. In this case, it was found that there was a statistically significant difference between the average scores they received ($t(,494) = ,0219, p < 0,01$).

A difference of 1.46 points was found between the average scores obtained by 3rd-grade students and 4th-grade students in the Critical Thinking and Problem Solving sub-skill, with the 3rd-grade students scoring less than the 4th-grade students. In this case, a statistically

significant difference was found between the average scores they received ($t(,793)= ,449$, $p<0,01$).

In the communication and collaboration sub-skill, there was a difference of 2.23 points between the average scores obtained by 3rd-year students and 4th-year students, to the disadvantage of the 3rd-year students. In this case, a statistically significant difference was determined between the average scores they received ($t(,694)= ,048$, $p<0,01$).

3.4. Findings Regarding the Fourth Sub-Problem

The findings for the fourth sub-problem are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. T-Test Results Regarding Critical and Creative Thinking Sub-Skills Based on Observation Results

Variables	N	X	SD	t	p	ES
Observation	21	69,76	5,99	22,15	,000	7,33
Creative Thinking	21	38,04	1,24			
Observation	21	69,76	5,99	15,12	,000	4,64
Critical Thinking	21	48,52	2,42			
Observation	21	69,76	5,99	42,33	,000	13,15
Maturity and Open-mindedness	21	11,80	1,72			
Observation	21	69,76	5,99	43,05	,000	12,68
Caution and Skepticism	21	15,04	1,16			
Observation	21	69,76	5,99	38,27	,000	12,53
Curiosity and Inquiry	21	15,04	1,49			
Observation	21	69,76	5,99	49,31	,000	14,79
Bias and Objectivity	21	6,61	,74			

A statistically significant difference was found between creative thinking, one of the sub-skills, and the observation results [$t(20)=22.15$, $p<0.001$]. This difference was found to have a strong effect size in favor of the observational results ($ES=7.33$).

A statistically significant difference was determined between critical thinking, one of the sub-skills, and the observation results [$t(20)= 15.12$, $p<0.001$]. This difference was found to have a strong effect size in favor of the observational results ($ES=4.64$).

A statistically significant difference was found between the observation results and the sub-skills of maturity and open-mindedness [$t(20)= 42.33$, $p<0.001$]. This difference was determined to have a strong effect size in favor of the observation results ($ES=13,15$).

A statistically significant difference was determined between the observation results and the sub-skills of being careful and suspicious [$t(20)= 43.05$, $p<0.001$]. This difference was found to have a strong effect size in favor of the observational results ($ES=12.68$).

A statistically significant difference was found between the results of observation and the sub-skills of curiosity and inquiry [$t(20)= 38.27$, $p<0.001$]. This difference was determined to have a strong effect size in favor of the observation results ($ES=12.53$).

It was found that there was a statistically significant difference between bias/objectivity and observation results among the sub-skills [$t(20)= 49.31$, $p<0.001$]. This difference was found to have a strong effect size in favor of the observational results ($ES=14.79$).

The findings revealed a statistically significant difference in the sub-skills of critical thinking and creative thinking among students educated in combined classes, according to observation results.

4. Results and Discussion

An evaluation of the scales used in the study revealed that participants performed better at critical thinking than creative thinking. In their study, Demirtaş et al. (2018) concluded that there was an increase in students' questioning, elaboration, and qualitative aspects. This result was consistent with the findings of the study. The research revealed that female students performed better than male students in skills such as providing justifications, making comparisons, and establishing relationships and similarities; however, the difference in scores was not significant. A significant difference was found between female students and male students in terms of critical thinking skills and creative thinking skills. No studies examining the sub-dimensions of critical thinking in terms of various variables have been found in the literature; only the effect of gender on critical thinking skills has been investigated. Various studies have found that female students are better at using critical thinking skills than male students (Walsh and Hardy, 1999; Kürüm, 2002; Ay and Akgöl, 2008). In their research, Demir (2006) and Akar and Kara (2016) found that the critical thinking skills of primary school students did not differ according to gender.

As the grade level increased, students' thinking skills scores also increased. Many studies have shown that age does not affect creative thinking skills (Ömeroğlu, 1986; Mehrotra and Sawyers, 1989). Avoiding any external influences during the observation process contributed to the reliability of the scores obtained from the scales. Although the scores for the sub-skills of critical and creative thinking, maturity and open-mindedness, attentiveness and skepticism, curiosity and inquiry, and bias/objectivity varied depending on the observation results, consistent results were obtained in terms of overall assessment.

The study found a moderate correlation between teachers' creative thinking tendencies and their behaviors aimed at encouraging creativity. This result shows that as teachers' tendencies towards creative thinking increase, their behaviors aimed at encouraging creativity will also increase. It was also observed that students were able to acquire skills in concrete operational thinking and the sub-dimensions of critical thinking. It can be said that teachers, family, and environmental factors can all have an influence on critical thinking skills. In their research, Tahiroğlu and Gevrek (2021) explained that family attitudes and behaviors have an effect on children's display of critical thinking skills. The study found no significant difference in creative thinking levels between genders; however, there was a significant difference in critical thinking skills in favor of female students. Ay and Akgöl (2008) found in their research that female students had higher critical thinking skills than male students. Studies by Çıkrıkçı (1996), Kaya (1997), Gelen (1999), Kürüm (2002), and Saracaloğlu et al. (2003) have shown that female students have higher critical thinking skills than male students.

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